

ISic1180

Funerary inscription for (?)Marcus Flavius Tuendus

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

stone

Object

unknown

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,system,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Halaesa

Place of origin (modern)

near Castel di Tusa

Provenance

Dug up in 1771 in the ruins of ancient Halaesa; recorded in 1784 as preserved at Montereale (= Monreale?), 'in monasterio Canonicorum regularium Benedictinae familiae'; now lost?

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, lost

Physical Description

No description of the stone is preserved

Dimensions

Height unknown cm

Width unknown cm

Depth unknown cm

Layout

The text is recorded in the antiquarian tradition over 6 lines

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

No description exists, but Castelli 1784 transcribes with lunate sigma and mostly lunate epsilon

Letter heights:

Line 1-6: unknown mm

Interlineation

Interlineation: unknown mm

Text

1. Φιλίππου
2. Φίλιππος
3. Σεκόνδος
4. Μᾶρ(κος) Φλουάβ
5. ιος Τουένδος
6. χᾶϊρε

Apparatus

Text of Castelli 1784

Translation (en)

Philippus Secundus, son of Philippus; Marcus Flavius Tuendus, greetings

Commentary

Castelli observed that the first three lines were unusual, seemingly recording the patronymic first. Franz in CIG proposed correcting the end of lines 1 and 2 so that the order was reversed. Kaibel in IG instead despaired of making sense of what he assumed to be either errors of Castelli or the result of a forgery. It is unclear whether this is in fact one individual with multiple names with the patronymic unusually placed first, or two separate individuals. Without the possibility of checking the stone, no certainty is possible. Tuendus is not a common name but is attested in Italy in the imperial period, and the text must be imperial in date (second to fourth century?). Facella (2006: 290 n.41) notes the various attestations of Secundus as a name in the imperial period in Sicily.

Digital identifiers:

TM 492785

EDCS 39102334

PHI 140663

URI <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic1180>

DOI 10.5281/zenodo.4021547

Bibliography

Kaibel, G. 1890. *Inscriptiones Graecae Siciliae et Italiae, additis graecis Galliae Hispaniae, Britanniae, Germaniae inscriptionibus. Inscriptiones Graecae consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae Editae. Volumen XIV.* Berlin. At 14.0358 (<https://clio.columbia.edu/catalog/6873760>)

Castelli, Gabriello Lancellotto, Principe di Torremuzza 1784. *Siciliae et objacentium insularum veterum inscriptionum nova collectio prolegomenis et notis illustrata, et iterum cum emendationibus, & auctariis evulgata.* Palermo. At cl.14 no.113

Boeckh, A., Franz, J., Curtius, E., Kirchhoff, A., Roehl, H. 1828-1887. *Corpus Inscriptionum Graecarum.* Berlin. At 3.5600

Facella, A. 2006. *Alesa Arconidea: ricerche su un'antica città della Sicilia tirrenica.* Pisa. At 290

Prag, J.R.W., Tigano, G. 2017. *Alesa Archonidea : il lapidarium. Introduzione all'archeologia di Halaesa.* Palermo. At no.47

Licensed under a Creative

Commons-Attribution 4.0 licence.

Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-18): ISic1180. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI

edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4351737>

